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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR: AN OVERVIEW OF INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool that harnesses anthropomorphic knowledge and provides expedited solutions to complex challenges. Remarkable advancements in AI technology and machine learning present a transformative opportunity in the drug discovery, formulation, and testing of pharmaceutical dosage forms. By utilizing AI algorithms that analyze extensive biological data, including genomics and proteomics, researchers can identify disease-associated targets and predict their interactions with potential drug candidates. AI has come a long way in healthcare, having played significant roles in data and information storage and management – such as patient medical histories, medicine stocks, sale records, and so on; automated machines; software and computer applications like diagnostic tools such as MRI radiation technology, CT diagnosis and many more have all been created to aid and simplify healthcare measures. This enables a more efficient and targeted approach to drug discovery, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful drug approvals. Furthermore, AI can contribute to reducing development costs by optimizing research and development processes. This capability enables the prioritization and optimization of lead compounds, reducing the need for extensive and costly animal testing. Personalized medicine approaches can be facilitated through AI algorithms that analyze real-world patient data, leading to more effective treatment outcomes and improved patient adherence. This review provides an overview of various AI-based approaches utilized in pharmaceutical technology, highlighting their benefits and drawbacks. Nevertheless, the continued investment in and exploration of AI in the pharmaceutical industry offer exciting prospects for enhancing drug development processes and patient care.

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INTRODUCTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence (AI) has achieved human-level capabilities and continues to rapidly improve. For the pharmaceutical industry, AI can improve decision-making and transform the quest for better medicines. The keys are investing in data management and in internal AI talent who can create value by leveraging corporate data to tackle crucial business problems.

- According to Father of artificial Intelligence, “John McCarthy,” it is “*The science and engineering of making intelligent machines*”.
- Artificial Intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence that exhibited by machines or especially computer software system.
- The process includes Learning, Reasoning, and self-correction.
- It stores large amount of information and process at a very high speed.
- AI technology is widely used throughout industry, government and science.
- AI is used in various sectors from innovating educational methods to automating business processes.[1]

Numerous industries are striving to enhance their progress to meet the demands and expectations of their customers, utilizing various methodologies. The pharmaceutical industry is a critical field that plays a vital role in saving lives. It operates based on continuous innovation and the adoption of new technologies to address global healthcare challenges and respond to medical emergencies, such as the recent pandemic. In the pharmaceutical industry, innovation is typically predicated on extensive research and development across various domains, including but not limited to manufacturing technology, packaging considerations, and customer-oriented marketing strategies. Novel pharmaceutical innovations are range from small drug molecules to biologics, with a preference for better stability with high potency to fulfil unmet needs to treat diseases. The assessment of the significant levels of toxicity associated with new drugs is an area of considerable concern, necessitating extensive research and exploration in the foreseeable future. One of the primary aims is to provide drug molecules that offer optimal benefits and suitability for utilization in the healthcare industry. Despite this, the pharmacy industry faces numerous obstacles that necessitate further advancement using technology-driven methods to address worldwide medical and healthcare demands [2].

ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FIELD OF PHARMACY

- Artificial intelligence is being introduced in the medical field to keep medical record in digital format and conduct patient checkup using smart technologies.
- It is one of the top technologies shaping the future of pharmacy.
- A Pharmacy industry has been developing cure & treatment for centuries. Traditionally the design & manufacturing of drug requires several years.
- AI is an innovative technology that helps to guide the surgeon during medication, treatment and operation.
- This technology is for better decision-making for complicated cases.
- Artificial intelligence can be integrated to simplify the complexity of pharmaceutical industry.
- The current pharmacy environment is expensive and lengthy drug discovery cycles and clinical trials with pricing pressures by both payers and consumers.
- The Average cost to research and develop each drug is estimated to be \$4 billion.
- The cost of failure of the thousands and millions of compounds.
- The overall probability of the clinical success is estimated to be 7.9%
- Thus, with the rise of 21st century technologies, this has been changing due to Artificial Intelligence.
- In future we will see completely different drug designs, manufacture & clinical trials.[3-4]

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACY SECTOR

Figure 1: APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.

Drug Discovery Process and Design

The use of AI in the pharmaceutical industry for the design and development of drugs is increasing. From making small molecules to determining novel biological targets, AI plays a prominent role in drug target identification and validation. It is widely used for multi-target drug innovation and biomarker identification in an efficient way with great accuracy.

For example, researchers in pharmaceutical can identify and verify novel cancer drugs using data such as longitudinal EMR records (Electronic Medical Records) and other omic data. The AI systems using ML and other data analytics algorithms will extract insights from EMR data and creates the best formulations to design and develop drugs that cure tumours well. [5]

Research & Development

Pharmacy companies across the globe are using advanced AI-powered tools and ML algorithms to smoothen the drug research, development, and innovation process. These technology tools are designed to detect complex patterns in large datasets. Therefore, AI in pharmacy industry can be used to resolve problems associated with the research and development process.

This ability to study patterns of various diseases and to determine which composite formulations are best suited for the treatment of specific symptoms of a particular disease is excellent. Pharmacy industries can invest in the R&D of such drugs that are more likely to treat a disease or medical condition successfully. [5]

Disease Prevention

Pharmaceutical organizations can use Artificial intelligence to develop medicines Parkinson's and Alzheimer's and very rare diseases.

As per Global Genes, it is a fact that almost 95% of rare diseases do not have more drugs to treat and cure faster. However, thanks to the innovative capabilities of AI and ML. The use of AI in the pharmaceutical industry will completely transform this scenario and ensure the most-advanced models for detecting hazardous diseases in the early stage and improve patient outcomes. [6]

Next-Level Diagnosis

Physicians can use advanced machine learning systems to gather, process, and analyze patient health care data. Healthcare professionals across the globe are using deep learning and ML to securely store patient data in the centralized storage system or cloud. It is called Electronic Medical Records (EMR).

Physicians may refer to these health records when they need to understand the effect of a specific genetic trait on a patient's health or how medicine treats it. Machine Learning systems can use data stored in EMRs to generate real-time estimates for diagnostic purposes and to indicate appropriate treatment for the patient. As ML technologies are capable of processing and analyzing large amounts of data quickly, they can help speed up the diagnostic process, thereby saving millions of lives. [6]

Epidemic Prediction

Pharmacy companies and healthcare industries are using ML and AI technologies to monitor and assess the spread of infections worldwide. These modern technologies are used for consuming data collected from various resources, analyzing several environmental, biological, and geographical factors on the population health of diverse geographical regions, and deriving data insights to reduce the impact of epidemics in the future. Artificial intelligence and machine learning models are particularly beneficial for underdeveloped economies that lack medical infrastructure and financial framework to combat the spread of infection.

A good example of this is the ML-based malaria outbreak prediction model, which serves as a warning tool for malaria outbreaks and helps health care providers take the best action to combat it. [6]

Identifying Clinical Trials

It is one of the key pharmaceutical use cases for embracing AI into existing models. The use of AI in the pharmaceutical industry for identifying drug candidates which are under final clinical trials from vast clinical data is on the rise.

Artificial Intelligence in Pharmaceutical Industry will help companies in analyzing thousands of samples in minutes and automatically logs data related to how patients are responding during clinical trials.

Here are a few advantages of using AI in pharmacy industry for clinical trials:

- AI applications or systems analyze historic clinical data
- AI apps help in monitoring drug performance and evaluating drug responses
- With the integration of speech recognition technologies, AI apps for pharma will be helpful for recording patients' oral text during drug trial phases. It means that AI applications will record patients' responses.

Hence, the use of artificial intelligence in clinical trials has the potential in fastening clinical trials and introduces the safest drugs into the market. It is also one of the top use cases for Machine Learning in Pharma. Speech analysis and real-time patient and drug monitoring activities will be done accurately using ML, deep learning, and natural language processing technologies. [7]

Drug Adherences and Dosage

The adoption of AI in Pharmaceuticals and Healthcare is increasing at a rapid pace for identifying the right amount of drug intake to ensure the safety of drug consumers. AI technology will monitor patients during clinical trials and suggest the right amount of dosage at regular intervals. These are all key pharmaceutical use Cases for Embracing AI. AI in Pharmaceuticals and Healthcare will definitely accelerate automation in processes and drive more accuracy than ever before. These AI trends & use cases in pharmacy will assist drug development and healthcare companies in ensuring efficacy across end-to-end production lines and delivering top-notch performance in front of the FDA. [7]

WHAT IS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY?

The possible applications of AI in the drug development pipeline in drug development strategies and processes, the pharmaceutical R&D efficiency and attrition, and partnerships between AI and pharmaceutical companies are discussed.

To understand the impact of AI technology, let's talk about what kind of technologies are called "AI" in a nutshell and what they are used for. Mainly, technology specialists define three directions:

- **Data science algorithms** These human-created automated algorithms are designed to analyze past activities and create alternative decisions. For example, it can provide a more effective treatment plan or drug combination based on the patient's clinical data and medical history.
- **Machine learning algorithms** are a more complicated way of decision-making analysis based on neural network analytics. It works with given datasets to predict decision consequences and categorize and classify information. This is a quick and reliable way to create marketing strategies or conduct clinical trials.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of Machine learning algorithms.

- **Deep learning** is based on more complicated forms of learning and natural language processing; it is used for more detailed diagnosis. It can analyze sensitive images like skin conditions or radiology scans and combine received data with historical treatment outcomes or other patient-specific information to create the most suitable solution.[8]

FUTURE OF PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

- AI is able to design new drugs
- Find new drug combination
- Deliver clinical trials within minutes
- Drugs are not tested on real humans or animals, but on virtual model that are engineered to mimic the physiology of organs.
- Robot help in the manufacturing of medication as well as their distribution.
- Local pharmacist's 3D prints personalized drugs in any shape & desired dosage [9]

PARTNERSHIPS BETWEEN THE PHARMACY INDUSTRY AND AI COMPANIES

With the rapid introduction of AI in healthcare, especially in the years 2016 and 2017, numerous pharmaceutical companies have made investments in and have joint ventures with AI companies in the hopes of developing better healthcare tools. These include the improvements in diagnostics or biomarkers and the identification of drug targets and designing new drugs. The transition from general medicine to modern AI healthcare focuses on the basis of the data. The analyses of these underlying data coupled with ML or DL are subsequently formulated into algorithms – thereby strongly contributing to progressive modern healthcare that incorporates AI. Thus, numerous partnerships between pharmaceutical industries and AI companies were recently developed on a global scale. For instance, Deep Mind Technologies, a subsidiary of Google, collaborated with Royal Free London NHS Foundation Trust to assist in the management of acute kidney injury. A global project that utilises data and AI from NHS patients with rare diseases is England's 100 000 Genomes Project; this project is in collaboration with Roche, Berg, Merck and Biogen. [10].

Figure 3: Companies Collaborate with AI.

AI IN PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET - GLOBAL INDUSTRY ANALYSIS, SIZE, SHARE, GROWTH, TRENDS, REGIONAL OUTLOOK, AND FORECAST 2021 – 2030

The global AI in pharmaceutical market was valued at USD 905.91 million in 2021 and is expected to **reach over USD 9,241.34 million by 2030**, poised to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of **29.4% from 2022 to 2030**.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of Pharmaceutical Market.

Growth Factors

The automated and the interconnected technologies that can function automatically with minimum or no human intervention, in the pharmaceutical industry are referred to as the AI in the pharmaceutical.

The AI can significantly enhance the operations related to manufacturing, clinical trials, and research & development. It is estimated that more than 60% of the healthcare companies across the globe are planning to implement artificial intelligence technologies, during the forecast period. The rising adoption of the AI in the biotechnology and the healthcare industry is expected to be a major factor behind the burgeoning growth of the market. The top companies in the pharmaceutical industry are joining hands with the players in the AI industry to implement AI technology in the drug discovery, research and development, and drug manufacturing. Top companies such as Pfizer, Sanofi, GSK, and AstraZeneca are either collaborating with the AI companies or acquiring the AI technologies. Therefore, the heavy investments by the top healthcare companies are exponentially fuelling the growth of the global AI in the pharmaceutical market.

The growth of the AI in pharmaceutical market is attributable to the rising healthcare expenditure, favourable government policies, and strong economic growth in the past few years, especially in the emerging markets. The AI in the pharmaceutical market witnessed a sudden spike in 2020 owing to the increased investments in the AI for discovering the drugs for the COVID-19 disease. For instance, in April 2020, GSK entered into a partnership with Viral Biotechnology to enhance the process of drug discovery for COVID-19 through AI and CRISPR. Hence, the outbreak of the COVID-19 diseases has resulted in the growth of the market in 2020 and this growth is expected to sustain and have a great impact on the market growth during the forecast period.

“The deep learning was the dominant segment in the global AI in the pharmaceutical market, garnering a market share of over 34% in 2022”. Deep learning can efficiently identify the certain health conditions that develop in the body and can predict regarding the health conditions accurately. Deep learning technology covers the procedures such as cardiovascular diseases, sepsis, and thyroidectomy, which has significantly fostered the growth of this segment. The increased usage of the deep learning technology in the diagnosis and prediction of the health conditions has led to the dominance of this segment. [11-12]

SCOPE OF THE AI IN PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET [13]

SR.NO	Report Coverage	Details
1	Market Size in 2020	USD 701.6 Million
2	Growth Rate from 2021 to 2030	29.4%
3	Revenue Projection by 2030	USD 9,241.34 Million
4	Largest Market	North America
5	Fastest Growing Market	Asia Pacific
6	Base Year	2021
7	Forecast Period	2021 to 2030
8	Companies Mentioned	IBM Corporation, Exscientia, Deep Genomics, Cloud Pharmaceuticals Inc., Microsoft Corporation, NVIDIA Corporation, Insilico Medicine, Alphabet Inc., Atomwise Inc., Biosymetrics, Euretos, BenevolentAI

RISKS & DISADVANTAGE ASSOCIATED WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

High cost –

Creation of AI requires huge costs as they are very complex machines.

Unemployment –

AI can cause unemployment as things would be automated in this system as there is need of less human labor. [14]

No match for human Brain intelligence –

Finally, AI systems cannot process human emotions and feel them. It is highly challenging to incorporate ethics and morality into these systems. Advanced versions of AI like the theory of mind and Self-awareness, when achieved, can only implement ethical behaviour in AI systems. [15]

No improvement with experience –

Human resources can be improved with experiences. In contrast, machines with AI technology cannot be enhanced with experience. They cannot identify which individual is hard-working and which one is nonworking.

No original creativity –

Machines with AI technology have neither sensitivity nor emotional intelligence. Humans can hear, see, feel and think. They can use their creativity as well as thoughts. These features are not achievable by the use of machines.

Addiction –

As we rely depends on machines to make everyday tasks more efficient we use machines.

Lack of personal connections –

Since AI systems make predictions based on a set of algorithms, these can lack creativity, especially in the content **marketing** field. As AI systems improve over time from inputs and experience, they cannot think outside the box or generate creative approaches to a project.[16]

Increase Human Laziness –

Automation in tasks and increased availability of digital assistants tend to increase machine dependency, which can likely increase human laziness. Too much relying on AI for simple tasks such as small calculations or remembering numbers or addresses can affect humans in their day-to-day activities, which require memorization or analysis. Conscious use of AI is crucial to avoid negative effects on future generations.

Susceptible to security risks-

As AI is generally dependent on data networks; AI systems are susceptible to security risks. The onset of Offensive AI, improved cyber security will be required to ensure the technology is sustainable. According to **Forrester Consulting**, 88% of decision-makers in the security industry are convinced offensive AI is an emerging threat.[17]

Change can be difficult –

In any industry, change can prove challenging. Since the healthcare industry is crucial for patient care, the medical community need proof that AI will be effective, as well as a plan to show investors it is going to be worth the cost. Everyone working alongside AI technology will need to have an understanding of this technology and how it can assist them with day-to-day tasks.

Insufficient Comprehension of Context –

AI systems might find it difficult to properly understand the context and subtleties of medical communication. They can create material using patterns and statistics but may not fully comprehend the complications. Real medical writers have industry experience and can provide information efficiently, resulting in communications that are thorough and useful.[18]

Human Oversight and Perception –

Even though AI may computerize certain elements of medical writing, it cannot completely take the place of human influence. Critical thinking, individual interpretation, and broad choice-making are all aspects of medical writing that demand for human skill.[19]

Taking Moral and Legal Issues into Consideration-

There are ethical questions raised over AI-developed material, including, accountability, and prejudices. [20]

CONCLUSION

AI is transforming drug delivery technologies, enabling targeted, personalized, and adaptive therapies. By leveraging AI's capabilities in data analysis, pattern recognition, and optimization, pharmaceutical researchers and healthcare professionals can enhance drug efficacy, minimize side effects, and improve patient outcomes. They offer several advantages over traditional experimental methods. AI-based models can predict pharmacokinetic parameters, simulate drug distribution and clearance in the body, and optimize drug dosage and administration routes. AI-based computational methods for PBPK models can simplify the development of such models and optimize their parameters, reducing the need for animal studies and human clinical trials. Computational pharmaceuticals, facilitated by AI and big data, revolutionizes the drug delivery process by providing a more efficient, cost-effective, and data-driven approach. It enables the optimization of drug formulations, personalized therapies, regulatory compliance, and risk reduction, ultimately leading to improved drug manufacturing processes and enhanced patient outcomes. Overall, the integration of AI technologies holds great promise for accelerating drug development, improving patient outcomes, and revolutionizing the pharmaceutical industry.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

Nil

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